

TRANSLATION OF MODAL VERBS IN NEWSPAPERS

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ANNOTATION. This article provides general information about the grammatical features of modal verbs, their place in the sentence, and their use. There was also talk about the methodological problems of modal verbs when they are used in newspaper articles and their translation.

Key words: translation, newspaper, verbs, modal verbs, noun.

Modality is expression of speaker's attitude to what his utterance denotes. The speaker's judgment may be of different kinds, that is, the speaker may express various modal meanings. Modal verbs unlike other verbs, do not denote actions or states, but only show the attitude of the speaker towards the action expressed by the infinitive in combination with which they form compound modal predicates. These modal verbs may show that the action (or state, of process, or quality) is viewed by the speaker as possible, obligatory, doubtful, certain, permissible, advisable, requested, prohibited, ordered etc. Modal verbs occur only with the infinitive. This or that meaning is to a great degree determined by communicative type of the sentence and the form of the infinitive. That is a huge problem for foreign learners of English, who make a great deal of mistakes in this field. So, the aim of my work is to show how modal verbs can be used, in what case we need one or other verb and why.

English modality can be expressed not only by modal verbs. Modality can be expressed by different linguistic means. In actual speech all forms expressing modality work together to make the meaning clear. But in every case there is some leading form that expresses the main attitude. These forms fall into four categories: phonetic (intonation), grammatical (mood), lexico-grammatical (modal verbs), lexical (modal words and phrases). But the most important from them is the third form, which includes modal verbs. It is important to take into account one more feature peculiar to modal verbs. They all show that a certain action is represented as necessary, doubtful, etc. From the point of view of the speaker, there are verbs which 'help' other verbs to express a meaning: it is important to realize that "modal verbs" have no meaning by themselves. A modal verb such as *would* has several varying functions; it can be used, for example, to help verbs express ideas about the past, the present and the future. It is therefore wrong to simply believe that "*would* is the past of *will*": it is many other things.

The meanings of modal verbs are extremely important for understanding how modal verbs work. This or that modal verb in one of its meanings can't form the past tense; in another meaning it is used only with a negative; in still another meaning it can't form a question or, on the contrary, is used only in the form of a question.

There are nine common modal verbs in English. They are:

Can, could, may, might, must, shall, should, will, would.

Modal verbs always appear in the first position at the beginning of the verb phrase in English. Unlike other verbs, modal verbs do not show tense or number.

Modal verbs are difficult to define in any language because of the wide range of pragmatic uses of modal verbs by native speakers. Some of the more common definitions (in no particular order) of the modal verbs in English are:

can – ability, permission, possibility, request

could – ability, permission, possibility, request, suggestion

may – permission, probability, request

might – possibility, probability, suggestion

must – deduction, necessity, obligation, prohibition

shall – decision, future, offer, question, suggestion

should – advice, necessity, prediction, recommendation

will – decision, future, intention, offer, prediction, promise, suggestion

would – conditional, habit, invitation, permission, preference, request, question, suggestion

Modal verbs are also called modal auxiliaries or modals. Modal verbs are sometimes called defective verbs, because they do not have all the functions of main verbs or auxiliary verbs. They can't be used without a main verb, can't form gerunds or participles, and do not have any endings to show person, number, or tense. Modal verbs form questions without the help of the other auxiliary verbs. Some modal verbs are rarely used in questions. Modal verbs also have quite a few peculiarities in the formation of tenses:

1. Labour **may** have helped a major donor to avoid tax by accepting a gift from him in shares, it emerged last night. John Mills gave the party £1.65 million in shares in JML, his retail company, in January — the biggest donation Labour...

- Mehnat Mehnatkashlar undan sovg'a olish evaziga uni katta soliq to'lovlaridan qutilishga yordam berishlari mumkin edi. (The times UK)

New mobile technologies **could cut** €100billion from EU health budgets and increase GDP by €93billion by 2017, it has been claimed. – Yangi mobil texnologiyalari Yevropa hamjamiyati sog'lik byudjetidan 100 mln yevroni sarflanishiga sabab bo'lishi mumkin edi.(The telegraph).

By [Matt Warman](#), Consumer Technology Editor

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The most important use of substitute phrases is in those cases where modal verbs can't be used. For example, the modal verb must in the meaning "strong necessity" doesn't have the past form, so the substitute phrase have to (necessity) is typically used instead of the modal verb MUST in the past tense, with a little change in meaning.

The meanings of modal verbs are a little difficult to single out and define clearly (especially if we try to define them in Russian). For example, when speaking about the main meaning of the verb CAN, some linguists use the words "ability, possibility", others speak about "physical and mental ability", still others say "ability, power, skill, opportunity". The material Overview of Modal Verbs describes the meanings of modal verbs in general, and typical examples of use are given. The materials on specific modal verbs describe their meanings, usage, and peculiarities in detail. Specific modal verbs are grouped by their meaning in the materials of this section, e.g., Ability, Advice, Necessity.

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